

**INTERNATIONAL
ONLINE SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE**

**GlobalMed 2026:
Multidisciplinary Advances in
Modern Medicine**

January 30, 2026

Turkey

CONTENTS

Madzhidova Ya.N., Zaidova A.Kh.	PROSPECTS FOR THE USE OF NEUROSTIMULATION AND PHOTOBIO-MODULATION IN CHILDHOOD ENURESIS: NEUROLOGICAL ASPECT	23
Ismatov Jamshed Karimovich	IMPROVEMENT OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF TRACHEAL CIRCUMFERENTIAL STENOSIS TAKING INTO ACCOUNT IMMUNOLOGICAL PREDICTORS OF RESTENOSIS	25
Irina V. Haidukevich, Tatsiana S. Golubeva, Inna M. Halayenka, Victor G. Obedkov, Olga S. Bokut, Gennady V. Sergeev, Tatsiana V. Dakukina	HIGH-RISK GENETIC PROFILES FOR PHARMACORESISTANT SCHIZOPHRENIA: INSIGHTS FROM BELARUSIAN PATIENTS	28
Hikmatov Jasur, Gulnazarov Islom, Mardanova Munisa	ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN MEDICAL EDUCATION: A NEW PARADIGM IN SHAPING CLINICAL THINKING	30
Safarov Jasur Temirovich	IMMUNOLOGICAL PREDICTORS OF COMPLICATIONS AFTER TRANSVERTEBRAL FIXATION IN PATIENTS WITH SPONDYLOLISTHESIS	33
Ekaterina Sorokina, Ekaterina Chernevskaya, Alisa Pautova	GUT MICROBIOTA AND SYSTEMIC INFLAMMATION IN POST-COVID-19 PATIENTS	35
Makrina Katsanopoulou, Anna Ofrydopoulou, Alexandros Tsoupras	ANTI-INFLAMMATORY AND ANTIPLATELET EFFECTS OF NSAIDS AND CLOPIDOGREL ON PAF AND ADP PATHWAYS: IN VITRO ASSESSMENT USING HUMAN PLATELETS	37
Axmedova Dildoraxon	THE CLINICAL PICTURE OF SPEECH AND MENTAL IMPAIRMENTS IN CHILDREN WITH SECONDARY ENCEPHALITIS	39

IMPROVEMENT OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF TRACHEAL CICATRICEAL STENOSIS TAKING INTO ACCOUNT IMMUNOLOGICAL PREDICTORS OF RESTENOSIS

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Cicatricial tracheal stenosis (CTS) is one of the most complex and socially significant problems of modern thoracic and otolaryngological surgery (Grillo H.C., 2003; Nouraei, S. A. R. et al., 2007). This pathology, as a rule, develops as a result of prolonged intubation, tracheostomy, mechanical damage to the trachea, as well as infectious and inflammatory processes leading to the formation of coarse scar tissue and progressive narrowing of the airways. The clinical course of RCT is accompanied by a violation of the ventilation function of the lungs, the development of chronic respiratory failure, a decrease in tolerance to physical activity and a significant deterioration in the quality of life of patients, and in some cases can pose an immediate threat to life (D'Andrilli, A., et al., 2014).

Despite significant advances in surgical technology and anesthetic management, treatment of cicatricial tracheal stenosis remains associated with a high rate of postoperative complications and recurrences, including restenosis at the anastomotic site (Wright, C. D., et al., 2019). Technical difficulties in forming the tracheotracheal anastomosis remain a key cause of unsatisfactory surgical outcomes, especially in cases of extensive stenosis and significant morphological changes in the tracheal tissue. Furthermore, increasing attention is being paid to the immunological mechanisms underlying pathological scarring, chronic inflammation, and subsequent restenosis after surgical interventions.

Objective of the study: To improve the method of applying tracheo-tracheal anastomosis during circular resection of the trachea in patients with cicatricial stenosis, as well as to study the immunological changes accompanying the develop-

ment of stenosis, in order to predict restenosis and develop individualized preventive tactics.

Material and Methods: The study was conducted at the Bukhara Regional Multidisciplinary Hospital and included 28 patients with cicatricial tracheal stenosis undergoing dynamic observation during surgical treatment. Depending on the surgical method used, the patients were divided into two groups: Group I - 15 patients who underwent surgical treatment using the standard method of creating a tracheotracheal anastomosis; Group II - 13 patients operated on using an improved method of forming anastomosis.

The study utilizes clinical examination methods, a comprehensive immunological study, and laboratory and instrumental diagnostic methods, including electrocardiography, echocardiography, complete blood counts, biochemical blood tests, coagulation profiles, lipid profiles, and bronchoscopy. Modern statistical analysis methods are used to objectively evaluate the data obtained, allowing us to determine the clinical efficacy of the proposed surgical approach and identify the relationship between immunological parameters and the development of restenosis.

Results and discussion: IN During a comparative analysis of the results of surgical treatment of 28 patients with cicatricial stenosis of the trachea, it was established that the use of an improved method of creating a tracheo-tracheal anastomosis is accompanied by a significant decrease in the incidence of postoperative restenosis. In Group I (standard technique, $n = 15$), tracheal restenosis within 12 months after circular resection was detected in 5 patients (33.3%), while in Group II (improved technique, $n = 13$) this figure was 1 case (7.7%), indicating a 4.3-fold decrease in the recurrence rate ($p < 0.05$). In addition, the severity of local inflammatory reactions in the anastomotic zone, assessed by clinical and endoscopic data, was significantly lower in patients of Group II, where signs of chronic inflammation were noted in 15.4% of patients versus 46.7% in the standard treatment group ($p < 0.05$). The obtained results indicate more favorable conditions for tracheal wall

healing when using a modified surgical technique.

An analysis of the patients' immunological status demonstrated that those who developed restenosis in the postoperative period demonstrated statistically significant changes in systemic inflammatory response parameters. In particular, preoperatively, patients in Group I with subsequent restenosis demonstrated an increase in proinflammatory cytokine levels by an average of 28–35% compared to uncomplicated patients, while in Group II, such changes were detected in only one case. The use of immunological parameters as prognostic criteria allowed us to identify a high-risk group for restenosis and implement targeted preventive measures. This, in turn, led to a decrease in the overall incidence of postoperative complications from 40.0% in Group I to 15.4% in Group II and a reduction in the average rehabilitation period from 21.6 ± 2.4 to 14.3 ± 1.8 days ($p < 0.05$). Thus, the integration of an improved surgical technique with immunological monitoring increases the effectiveness of treatment and significantly reduces the risk of recurrence of cicatricial tracheal stenosis after resection.

Conclusions: This study confirms the feasibility of a comprehensive approach to the treatment of cicatricial tracheal stenosis, based on a combination of improved surgical techniques and assessment of the patient's immunological status. The use of a modified tracheotracheal anastomosis technique helps reduce the severity of inflammation in the surgical site and decrease the risk of restenosis in the postoperative period.

It has been established that analysis of immunological parameters allows for the identification of patients with an increased predisposition to complicated tracheal stenosis, paving the way for early prediction of restenosis and targeted preventive measures. The implementation of a personalized approach based on immunological predictors helps reduce the incidence of postoperative complications, shorten rehabilitation periods, and improve the overall effectiveness of surgical treatment for patients with cicatricial tracheal stenosis.

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International Online Scientific Conference

CERTIFICATE

ISMATOV JAMSHED KARIMOVICH

was awarded for his active participation in the scientific work on the topic

***“Improvement of Surgical Treatment of Tracheal
Cicatricial Stenosis Taking Into Account Immunological
Predictors of Restenosis”***

TURKEY, JANUARY 30, 2026

